

Effect of *Klebsiella oxytoca* Bacteria on the Growth of Fungi Contaminating Date Palm Tissue Culture Media (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.)

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Abstract

The study was conducted in the Fungi Laboratory, University of Kerbala / College of Agriculture, with the aim of molecularly identifying the bacteria *Klebsiella Oxytoca* and testing its efficiency in inhibiting the fungi contaminating palm samples in tissue culture, which are the fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Meyerozyma guilliermondii*, and testing their effect on the contamination rate and growth parameters (number of branches, fresh weight, dry weight). The results of the PCR analysis showed that the isolate belongs to the bacteria *K. Oxytoca* with a matching percentage of (100%), as the bacterial isolate was registered in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) under the accession code (PV022086.1). The results also showed the superiority of live cells in inhibiting fungal growth by a percentage of 92.60% for each of *A. flavus*, *P. chrysogenum* and *M. guilliermondii*. The filtrate for the sixth day at a concentration of 10% was also superior with a high inhibition percentage of 92.60% against the fungi *A. flavus* and *P. chrysogenum*, while the greatest effect of the filtrate on the third day was 75.92% on the fungus *P. chrysogenum*, compared to the control treatment, which reached 100%. The results also showed that adding the filtrate of the bacteria *K. Oxytoca* for the sixth day at concentrations of 5 and 10% on the tissue medium had a positive effect on all the studied traits, including the average number of branches, fresh weight and dry weight, which reached (20.67, 6.25 and 1.05 respectively) for the 10% concentration, while the contamination rate reached 0% for the two concentrations compared to the control treatment of 100%.

Keywords: *Klebsiella oxytoca*, Fungi Contaminating, *Phoenix dactylifera* L., Tissue Culture.

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Introduction

Chemicals play a crucial role in agriculture; however, excessive use leads to disruptions in the ecosystem, primarily causing soil and groundwater contamination. Additionally, chemical overuse negatively impacts beneficial soil microorganisms, resulting in reduced soil fertility and promoting pest resistance. Furthermore, chemical residues in agricultural products pose significant risks to human health (Mir et al.,

2022; Ahmad and Zaib, 2020). Therefore, priority should be given to alternative techniques that minimize reliance on chemical fertilizers. In this regard, the use of microorganisms serves as an excellent alternative to both chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Rasool et al., 2021; Hamid et al., 2021).

The soil microbial environment is more abundant than in any other ecosystem (Smalla et al., 2006), particularly in the rhizosphere, where many microorganisms act as plant growth promoters. These microbes produce hydrolytic enzymes, suppress plant-pathogenic fungi, and serve as alternatives to chemically synthesized compounds, thereby enhancing plant growth and nutrient uptake efficiency (Dutta and Podile, 2010). They contribute significantly to plant growth and development by producing plant growth regulators, bioactive compounds, and facilitating nutrient absorption (Singh et al., 2017). Their impact occurs through direct and indirect mechanisms, including the biosynthesis of phytohormones such as auxins, gibberellins, ethylene, cytokinins, and abscisic acid (Basu et al., 2021; Backer et al., 2018), as well as the solubilization of essential nutrients like potassium, zinc, and phosphorus, and the production of siderophores that enhance iron availability (Mir et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2019; Suleman et al., 2018).

The indirect effects of these microorganisms involve reducing infections caused by various plant pathogens by colonizing the rhizosphere and outcompeting other microbes through the production of antimicrobial compounds that inhibit their growth and development. This has been demonstrated in several bacterial genera, including *Pseudomonas*, *Azospirillum*, *Bacillus*, *Azotobacter*, *Arthrobacter*, *Klebsiella*, and *Enterobacter* (Nevita et al., 2018; Hamid et al., 2021). *Klebsiella oxytoca* has been shown to enhance plant growth and increase plant resistance, with Chowhan et al. (2023) reporting its high capability to produce the indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) hormone, along with strong ammonia production and high hydrocyanic acid (HCN) activity. Given that phosphorus is one of the most limiting nutrients for plant growth, *K. oxytoca* demonstrated the ability to solubilize tricalcium phosphate on NBRIP medium. Additionally, it exhibited strong enzymatic activity, including the production of protease, lipase, cellulase, and amylase, which have been proven effective in fungal inhibition. The present study focuses on isolating effective plant growth-promoting bacteria from the rhizosphere and evaluating their growth-promoting potential.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection and Bacterial Isolation

Soil samples were collected from the rhizosphere of actively growing offshoots in Al-Hindiya District, Kerbala Governorate, Iraq. The samples were then transported to the Plant Pathology Laboratory at the College of Agriculture, University of Kerbala.

Isolation was carried out by adding 1 g of soil to 9 ml of sterile distilled water and successive dilutions were made from 10^{-1} to 10^{-10} , where 1 ml of each dilution was added to plates containing the N.A. culture medium. Then the plates were incubated at 30°C , then the different colonies were purified morphologically on a new N.A. medium using the planning technique, after which the pure colonies were kept at 4°C in the refrigerator until work on them.

Molecular Diagnosis of Bacteria

In order to verify the type of bacteria, it was diagnosed at the DNA level. DNA was extracted, and the bacterial isolate was sent for molecular analysis to study the genetic and hereditary structure and compare it with the genome of global isolates. It was diagnosed by analyzing the DNA base sequence, as the PCR products were sent to Macrogen Company in South Korea to determine the nucleotide sequence in both forward and reverse directions. For the 16rRNA gene region, after receiving the nucleotide sequences of the bacterial isolates, the sequences were analyzed using the Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST) program to compare them with the data available in the NCBI within the electronic gene bank that belong

to the same bacterial isolates that were diagnosed globally. Then the bacterial isolates were registered, and nucleotide analyses were conducted using the MEGA X program to analyze the isolates and draw a kinship tree between each of these isolates and similar isolates registered at the NCBI Center. The phylogenetic tree of the Neighbor Joining type included that which was built from the molecular nucleotide sequence of the 16rRNA region belonging to the bacterial isolates.

In Vitro Antifungal Activity Testing of Bacteria

Four fungal contaminants of date palm tissue culture media, previously identified molecularly in the Plant Pathology Laboratory of the College of Agriculture, were tested to evaluate the antifungal activity of the isolated bacteria. Initially, the fungal isolates were activated on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) medium and incubated for 5 days. Subsequently, Nutrient Broth (N.B) medium was prepared and inoculated with the bacteria. After 24 hours, serial dilutions (10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , 10^{-5} , and 10^{-6}) were prepared and added to the pre-prepared PDA medium at a rate of 1 ml per plate. The plates were left to solidify and were then inoculated with the fungal contaminants of tissue culture media, namely *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, and *Mejeromyces guilliermondii*. These fungi were obtained from the Plant Pathology Laboratory of the College of Agriculture, University of Karbala. Each fungal species was tested in triplicate using a 0.5 cm cork borer, with a control treatment containing only the fungus. The plates were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 7 days. After incubation, the inhibition percentage of bacterial activity against fungal growth was measured using the following formula:

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{\text{Fungi growth rate in control} - \text{Fungi growth rate in treatment}}{\text{Fungi growth rate in control}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Preliminary Evaluation of *K. Oxytoca* Bacterial Filtrate Concentrations against Fungal Isolates in Laboratory Conditions

Preparation of Bacterial Filtrates

Four 250 ml conical flasks were prepared and liquid culture medium (Nutrient broth) was added to them, their nozzles were tightly closed and the flasks were sterilized by autoclave and then each one was inoculated by adding 1 ml of pure bacterial culture aged 24 hours and then incubated at a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ where the filtrate was taken from day 3 and 6 and then filtered through microfilters with 0.22 micrometer holes for two consecutive times to prevent the passage of living parts of the bacteria and then stored in the refrigerator until use.

Then the culture medium (PDA) was prepared and sterilized with an autoclave, then the filtrate was mixed at concentrations (0, 5, and 10) for days 3 and 6 with the nutritional medium, after which the plates were inoculated with pathogenic fungi at a rate of 3 replications for each concentration using a sterile 0.5 cm diameter puncher, with the presence of the control treatment in which the fungus was grown on the PDA medium only. Then the plates were incubated at a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 7 days, after which the result was taken by measuring the inhibition rate according to the following equation:

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{\text{Fungi growth rate in control} - \text{Fungi growth rate in treatment}}{\text{Fungi growth rate in control}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Effectiveness of Bacterial Filtrates in Protecting Tissue Culture Media and Palm Cells from Contamination

The method used was based on that of Murashige and Skoog (1962), utilizing the MS nutrient medium with a concentration of 4.33 g/L, supplemented with sucrose at a concentration of 60 g/L, vitamins, myo-inositol, and plant growth regulators specific to the multiplication stage. The volume was completed to 1 liter with distilled water, and the pH was adjusted to 5.7 ± 0.1 using hydrochloric acid (HCl). Agar was added at 7 g/L, and the medium was then placed on a magnetic hot plate stirrer to dissolve the agar and ensure uniformity. The medium was poured into 300 ml glass bottles, sealed tightly, and sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C and 15 psi for 20 minutes. After sterilization, the bottles were removed and allowed to cool before the medium solidified. The bacterial filtrates with concentrations of 0, 5, and 10 for the 6th day were then mixed into the medium.

The planting process was carried out inside a previously sterilized laminar air flow cabinet using 70% ethanol and UV light. Plant parts from pure cultures in the multiplication stage were transferred and planted on the nutrient medium. The bottles were sealed, and the plants were transferred to a growth chamber at a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The experiment was monitored every 3 days to ensure proper environmental conditions, observe plant growth, and check for fungal or bacterial contamination. Observations were recorded over a two-month period, including temperature, humidity, and any necessary adjustments. Growth parameters such as the number of branches, fresh weight, dry weight, and percentage of contamination were measured according to the following formula:

$$\text{Pollution \%} = \frac{\text{Number of culture bottles in which contamination appeared}}{\text{Number of culture bottles total}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Statistical analysis

After collecting and tabulating the data related to the study, it was statistically analyzed using a completely randomized design (CRD), and using the least significant difference test (L.S.D0.05) to compare and separate the averages (Al-Rawi and Khalaf Allah, 2000), using the statistical analysis program GenStat12.

Results and Discussion

Isolation and Diagnosis

The results of isolating and diagnosing bacteria from the root area of active suckers, which were distinguished by their green color and rapid growth, showed the presence of active bacterial colonies. These colonies were identified as Gram-negative bacteria of the *Klebsiella* genus, belonging to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, which are widely distributed in nature. The bacteria were non-motile and rod-shaped (Yang et al., 2022; Tomulescu et al., 2021). The presence of these bacteria alongside healthy suckers reflects their positive impact on both the plant and the microorganisms. Additionally, they contribute to the production of plant growth regulators, facilitate nutrient absorption, and provide other benefits (Singh et al., 2017). This particular type of bacteria was chosen due to its significant ability to enhance plant growth and the scarcity of studies addressing this topic.

Molecular Diagnosis of Bacteria

The results of molecular diagnosis using PCR technology for the bacterial isolate showed that the nucleotide sequence of the 16S rRNA confirmed that the bacterial isolate belongs to *K. oxytoca*. The analysis of the nucleotide sequence indicated a 100% match with global isolates present in the gene bank (NCBI). The nucleotide sequence of the bacterial isolate was deposited in the gene bank under the

accession number (PV022086.1). Nucleotide analyses were also conducted using the MEGA software to analyze the isolate's sequence and construct a phylogenetic tree to show the relationship between this isolate and similar isolates registered in the NCBI database. The tree was constructed from the nucleotide molecular sequence (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Phylogenetic Tree of the Bacterium *K. oxytoca*

In Vitro Antifungal Activity Testing of Bacteria

The concentrations of live cells of *K. oxytoca* significantly affected the inhibition of fungi contaminating the palm plant tissue culture medium in the laboratory. As shown in Table 1, the third dilution of the bacteria showed significant antifungal activity against the four fungal species, with high inhibition percentages. The inhibition rate was 92.60% for *P. chrysogenum*, *A. flavus*, and *M. guilliermondii*, while the inhibition rate for *A. niger* was 88.88%. In the fourth dilution, the inhibition rate was 88.90% for the three fungi *P. chrysogenum*, *A. flavus*, and *M. guilliermondii*, while it was 87.03% for *A. niger*. In the fifth dilution, the inhibition rate was 85.20% for *A. flavus*, *P. chrysogenum*, and *M. guilliermondii*, with a lower inhibition rate of 75.92% for *A. niger*. The sixth dilution showed inhibition rates ranging from 68.51% to 77.80% for the same fungal species compared to the control treatment, where the contamination by fungi alone showed 0.0% inhibition.

This effect is attributed to the activity of the bacteria and their secretion of bioactive substances that limit or inhibit fungal growth (Chowhan et al., 2023). Nogueira et al. (2019) mentioned that the results indicate that *K. pneumoniae* is capable of preventing spore germination and hyphal development of *Aspergillus*, likely depending on the physical interaction with the bacteria's metabolic activity. Additionally, Sakuda et al. (2024) discovered that *K. aerogenes* associated with peanut crops strongly inhibits aflatoxin production by *A. flavus* on peanuts briefly immersed in bacterial dilutions. The addition of bacteria inhibited aflatoxin production in peanuts, even at a dilution of 1×10^{-4} , indicating the bacteria's strong inhibitory activity, making it a promising candidate for an effective biocontrol agent.

Table 1. Role of *K. Oxytoca* Bacteria in the Growth of Fungal Isolates in the Laboratory

Seq	Treatments	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>M. guilliermondii</i>
1	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	1×10^{-3}	88.88	92.60	92.60	92.60
3	1×10^{-4}	87.03	88.90	88.90	88.90
4	1×10^{-5}	75.92	85.20	85.20	85.20

5	1×10 ⁻⁶	68.51	77.80	75.90	77.80
L.S.D		5.051	8.54	8.33	8.54

Note: That the numbers in the table represent inhibition percentages, and each number is the result of three replications.

Figure 2. Effect of Live Cells of *K. Oxytoca* Bacteria on the Growth of Fungal Isolates

In Vitro Antifungal Ability of Bacterial Filtrate Test

The results (see Table 2) revealed a significant effect of bacterial exudates on the growth of contaminated fungi on the third day, at two concentrations (5% and 10%). At the 5% concentration, the exudate significantly inhibited fungal growth, with a 74.07% inhibition rate on *P. chrysogenum*, and varying inhibition rates on other fungi, including *A. niger*, *A. flavus*, and *M. guilliermondii*, with inhibition rates of 51.90%, 59.30%, and 37.00%, respectively. The effect of the exudate increased with the 10% concentration, where the inhibition rate on *P. chrysogenum* reached 75.92%, while the inhibition on the remaining fungi ranged between 42.60% and 63.00%, compared to the control group, which consisted of the fungi alone, showing 0.0% inhibition.

Although there is a lack of sources on the effect of *K. oxytoca* exudates on fungi, previous studies have confirmed that *K. oxytoca* produces secondary metabolites that influence fungal growth and inhibit its development. Wang et al. (2023) reported the ability of *K. grimontii* to inhibit fungal growth, achieving a high inhibition rate of 72.27%. This bacterium inhibited the growth of *F. oxysporum*, reduced spore formation, and altered fungal morphology. Furthermore, it formed biofilm clusters on soybean root surfaces, proving its ability to prevent the growth of *F. oxysporum* on soybean seedlings.

Table 2. Role of the Prepared *K. Oxytoca* Filtrate after 3 Days in the Growth of Fungal Isolates

Seq	Treatments	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>M. guilliermondii</i>
1	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	R5	51.90	74.07	59.30	37.00
3	R10	59.30	75.92	63.00	42.60
L.S.D		7.27	5.13	7.27	13.28

Note: That the numbers in the table represent inhibition percentages, and each number is the result of three replications.

The results in Table 3 indicated that at a 10% concentration on the sixth day, the highest inhibition rate of 92.60% was observed for both *A. flavus* and *P. chrysogenum*. This was followed by an inhibition rate of approximately 87.03% for *A. niger*, while *M. guilliermondii* exhibited an inhibition rate of 79.62%. The findings also demonstrated that the bacterial exudate on the sixth day was more effective than on the third day in inhibiting the growth of contaminant fungi. The inhibition rates reached 88.90% and 87.00% for *P. chrysogenum* and *A. flavus*, respectively, followed by an 83.33% inhibition rate for *A. niger*. Meanwhile, the effect of the exudate on *M. guilliermondii* at a 5% concentration was 75.92%, compared to the control treatment (contaminant fungi alone), which showed no inhibition (0.0%).

Curtis et al. (2023) reported that exposure to *K. pneumoniae* exudate inhibits the growth of *A. fumigatus*. The interaction between them led to a reduction in spore germination and hyphal development, which was attributed to direct physical interactions between bacterial and fungal cells. Additionally, 35 compounds were identified as having potential effects on fungal growth and development. The inhibitory ability of *K. pneumoniae* exudate may also result from enzymatic activity. This experiment demonstrated that the bacterial exudate on the sixth day produced inhibition rates comparable to those of vegetative cells, whereas the third day showed slightly lower inhibition. The results also indicated that increasing the concentration led to higher inhibition rates. Moreover, the third dilution showed the highest inhibitory effect, followed by the fourth, fifth, and sixth dilutions.

Table 3. Role of the *K. Oxytoca* Bacteria Filtrate Prepared after 6 Days in the Growth of Fungal Isolates

Seq	Treatments	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>P. chrysogenum</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>M. guilliermondii</i>
1	Control	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	R5	83.33	88.90	87.00	75.92
3	R10	87.03	92.60	92.60	79.62
L.S.D		6.63	8.40	11.11	5.14

Note: That the numbers in the table are percentages of inhibition, and each number is the result of three replications.

Figure 3. Effect of *K. Oxytoca* Filtrate on the Growth of Fungal Isolates

Evaluation of the Efficiency of *K. Oxytoca* Bacteria Filtrate on Tissue Media

The results from Table 4 showed that the bacterial exudate of *K. oxytoca* on the sixth day had a positive impact on all studied traits. A significant increase in fresh weight was observed, reaching 6.25 g and 6.07 g for the 10% and 5% concentrations, respectively, compared to 2.70 g in the control treatment. Similarly, the dry weight was 1.05 g and 0.99 g for the 10% and 5% concentrations, respectively, whereas the dry weight in the control treatment was 0.52 g.

Furthermore, the bacterial exudate significantly increased the number of branches, with average values of 20.67 and 19.67 for the 10% and 5% concentrations, respectively, compared to 11.33 in the control treatment. This enhancement is attributed to the bacterial production of essential plant hormones such as auxin (IAA), along with its ability to fix nitrogen and solubilize phosphorus. Additionally, *K. oxytoca* can significantly enhance enzyme activity in the rhizosphere. Yang et al. (2021) reported that *K. oxytoca* reduces sodium content in maize seedlings while increasing potassium and calcium content, as well as the potassium/sodium and calcium/sodium ratios. Moreover, the bacterium substantially improves photosynthetic efficiency, salt and alkali tolerance, and promotes maize growth.

Table 4. Efficiency of *K. Oxytoca* Filtrate on Tissue Media

Seq	Treatments	No. Shoots and Branches	Fresh weight (g)	Dry weight (g)
1	Control	11.33	2.70	0.52
2	5%	19.67	6.07	0.99
3	10%	20.67	6.25	1.05
L.S.D		1.51	0.14	0.04

Note: The values in the table represent weights in grams and the average number of shoots, and each number is the result of three replications.

Figure 4. Effect of *K. oxytoca* Filtrate on the Growth of Cultured Date Palm Tissues

Khalifa et al. (2022) reported that *K. oxytoca* possesses multiple plant growth-promoting traits, including the production of indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), ACC deaminase activity, phosphate solubilization, and nitrogen fixation. In vitro inoculation of barley with *K. oxytoca* resulted in a significant increase in root and shoot dry weights. Additionally, the contamination rate of culture bottles was 0% for both tested concentrations, whereas the contamination rate in the control treatment was 100%. This finding highlights the bacterium's strong ability to produce substances that inhibit or suppress the growth of microbial contaminants. Chowhan et al. (2023) also demonstrated that *K. oxytoca* enhances plant growth and increases resistance by producing IAA. The bacterium exhibited strong activity in ammonia and hydrogen cyanide (HCN) production, phosphate solubilization, and the synthesis of key enzymes, including protease, lipase, cellulase, and amylase. These enzymatic activities have been shown to effectively inhibit the growth of microbial contaminants.

Conclusion

The study concluded that *K. oxytoca* bacteria showed high efficiency in inhibiting the growth of fungi contaminating palm samples in tissue culture. It was observed that live cells of the bacteria showed a high inhibition capacity of 92.60% against the studied fungi. Moreover, the filtrate on the sixth day at a concentration of 10% showed a remarkable inhibitory effect against fungi, as the inhibition rate reached 92.60% against *A. flavus* and *P. chrysogenum*. Which led to a clear improvement in growth parameters reflecting a positive effect on palm growth.

References

- Ahmad, I., & Zaib, S. (2020). Mighty microbes: Plant growth promoting microbes in soil health and sustainable agriculture. In D. L. Sparks (Ed.), *Soil Health* (pp. 243–264). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-44364-1_14
- Al-Rawi, K. M., & Khalafallah, A. (2000). *Design and analysis of agricultural experiments*. Dar Al-Kutub for Printing and Publishing, University of Mosul, Republic of Iraq.
- Backer, R., Rokem, J. S., Ilangumaran, G., Lamont, J., Praslickova, D., Ricci, E., Subramanian, S., & Smith, D. L. (2018). Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria: Context, mechanisms of action, and roadmap to commercialization of biostimulants for sustainable agriculture. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9, 1473. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01473>
- Basu, A., Prasad, P., Das, S. N., Kalam, S., Sayyed, R. Z., Reddy, M. S., & El Enshasy, H. (2021). Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) as green bioinoculants: Recent developments, constraints, and prospects. *Sustainability*, 13(3), 1140. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031140>
- Chowhan, L. B., Mir, M. I., Sabra, M. A., El-Habbab, A. A., & Kumar, B. K. (2023). Plant growth promoting and antagonistic traits of bacteria isolated from forest soil samples. *Iranian Journal of Microbiology*, 15(2), 278–289. <https://doi.org/10.18502/ijm.v15i2.12480>
- Curtis, A., Ryan, M., & Kavanagh, K. (2023). Exposure of *Aspergillus fumigatus* to *Klebsiella pneumoniae* culture filtrate inhibits growth and stimulates gliotoxin production. *Journal of Fungi*, 9(2), 222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof9020222>
- Dutta, S., & Podile, A. R. (2010). Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR): The bugs to debug the root zone. *Critical Reviews in Microbiology*, 36(3), 232–244. <https://doi.org/10.3109/10408411003766806>
- Hamid, B., Zaman, M., Farooq, S., Fatima, S., Sayyed, R. Z., Baba, Z. A., Sheikh, T. A., Reddy, M. S., El Enshasy, H., & Gafur, A. (2021). Bacterial plant biostimulants: A sustainable way towards improving

growth, productivity, and health of crops. *Sustainability*, 13(5), 2856. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052856>

Khalifa, A. Y. Z., & Aldayel, M. F. (2022). Isolation and characterization of *Klebsiella oxytoca* from the rhizosphere of *Lotus corniculatus* and its biostimulating features. *Brazilian Journal of Biology*, 82, e266395. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1519-6984.266395>

Mir, M. I., Hameeda, B., Quadriya, H., Kumar, B. K., Ilyas, N., Kee, Z. A. T., & Sayyed, R. Z. (2022). Multifarious indigenous diazotrophic rhizobacteria of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) rhizosphere and their effect on plant growth promotion. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 8, 781764. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.781764>

Murashige, T., & Skoog, F. (1962). A revised medium for rapid growth and bio assays with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiologia Plantarum*, 15(3), 473–497. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-3054.1962.tb08052.x>

Nevita, T., Sharma, G. D., & Pandey, P. (2018). Composting of rice-residues using lignocellulolytic plant-probiotic *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and its evaluation for growth enhancement of *Oryza sativa* L. *Environmental Sustainability*, 1, 185–196. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42398-018-0019-7>

Nogueira, M. F., Pereira, L., Jenull, S., Kuchler, K., & Lion, T. (2019). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* prevents spore germination and hyphal development of *Aspergillus* species. *Scientific Reports*, 9, 218. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-36493-3>

Rasool, A., Mir, M. I., Zulfajri, M., Hanafiah, M. M., Unnisa, S. A., & Mahboob, M. (2021). Plant growth promoting and antifungal asset of indigenous rhizobacteria secluded from saffron (*Crocus sativus* L.) rhizosphere. *Microbial Pathogenesis*, 150, 104734. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micpath.2020.104734>

Sakuda, S., Sunaoka, M., Terada, M., Sakoda, A., Ishijima, N., Hakoshima, N., & Furukawa, T. (2024). Inhibition of aflatoxin production in *Aspergillus flavus* by a *Klebsiella* sp. and its metabolite cyclo (L-Ala-Gly). *Toxins*, 16(3), 141. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins16030141>

Singh, S., Kumar, V., Sidhu, G. K., Datta, S., Dhanjal, D. S., Koul, B., & Singh, J. (2019). Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria from heavy metal contaminated soil promote growth attributes of *Pisum sativum* L. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 17, 665–671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bcab.2019.01.027>

Singh, V. K., Singh, A. K., & Kumar, A. (2017). Disease management of tomato through PGPB: Current trends and future perspective. *3 Biotech*, 7, 255. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-017-0878-3>

Smalla, K., Sessitsch, A., & Hartmann, A. (2006). The rhizosphere: Soil compartment influenced by the root. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology*, 56, 165–173. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6941.2006.00084.x>

Suleman, M., Yasmin, S., Rasul, M., Yahya, M., Atta, B. M., & Mirza, M. S. (2018). Phosphate solubilizing bacteria with glucose dehydrogenase gene for phosphorus uptake and beneficial effects on wheat. *PLoS ONE*, 13(9), e0204408. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0204408>

Tomulescu, C., Moscovici, M., Lupescu, I., Stoica, R. M., & Vamanu, A. (2021). A review: *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*. *Romanian Biotechnology Letters*, 26, 2567–2586.

Wang, S., Zheng, L., Gao, A., Xiao, Y., Han, Z., Pan, H., & Zhang, H. (2023). Antifungal activity of *Klebsiella grimontii* DR11 against *Fusarium oxysporum* causing soybean root rot. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 134(11), lxad245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jambio/lxad245>

Yang, J., Long, H., Hu, Y., Feng, Y., McNally, A., & Zong, Z. (2022). *Klebsiella oxytoca* complex: Update on taxonomy, antimicrobial resistance, and virulence. *Clinical Microbiology Reviews*, 35(1), e00006-21. <https://doi.org/10.1128/CMR.00006-21>

Yang, L. J., Wang, Y. F., Zhang, Y. F., Fu, J., Yu, L. H., Deng, J., & Yang, K. J. (2021). *Klebsiella oxytoca* improves resistance of maize seedlings to saline-alkali stress. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Fertilizers*, 27(6), 1044–1054. <https://doi.org/10.11674/zwyf.2021262>

